

BC-SIM-PL-009

SIMBIO-SYS Checkout#06

Test Summary

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1. Introduction

1.1. Scope

In this document we describe all the tests to be performed during the Instrument CheckOut (ICO) # 06 for the Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem (SIMBIO-SYS).

1.2. Reference Document

- [RD.1] BC-SIM-TN-003_-_Reports_and_Note_Layout_and_Flow,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/179)
- [RD.2] BC-SIM-GAF-MA-002 10 001 - SIMBIO-SYS User Manual
- [RD.3] BC-SIM-TR-018_-_HRIC_ICO#02_report,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/134](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/134)
- [RD.4] BC-SIM-TR-019_-_STC_ICO#02_report,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/138](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/138)
- [RD.5] BC-SIM-TR-025_-_HRIC_ICO#03_report,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/190](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/190)
- [RD.6] BC-SIM-TR-031_-_STC_ICO#04_report,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/208](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/208)
- [RD.7] BC-SIM-TR-032_-_HRIC_ICO#04_report,
[10.5281/zenodo.8366034](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8366034)
- [RD.8] BC-SIM-TR-041_-_STC_ICO#05_report,
[10.5281/zenodo.12515578](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12515578)
- [RD.9] BC-SIM-TR-042_-_HRIC_ICO#05_report
- [RD.10] BC-SIM-TN-008_-_SIMBIO-SYS_FOP_update_after_ICO#02,
[10.20371/INAF/TechRep/162](https://doi.org/10.20371/INAF/TechRep/162)
- [RD.11] BC-ASD-SP-00176

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1.3. Acronyms

APID	Application Process IDentifier
ASW	Application SoftWare
CSV	Comma Separated Values
FPA	Focal Plane Assembly
FOP	Flight Operation Procedure
HK	HouseKeeping
HRIC	High spatial Resolution Imaging Channel
ICO	Instrument CheckOut
LFB	Low Freq Behaviour
ME	Main Electronics
NECP	Near Earth Commissioning Phase
OBCP	On-Board Control Procedure
POR	Payload Direct Operation Request
PDS	Planetary Data System
PE	Proximity Electronics
PNG	Portable Network Graphics
PSC	Packet Sequence Control
SIMBIO-SYS	Spectrometers and Imagers for MPO BepiColombo Integrated Observatory SYStem
SSC	Source Sequence Count
STC	STereo imaging Channel
TC	Telecommand
TEC	Thermo-Electric Cooler
TM	Telemetry
VIHI	VISible and Hyper-spectral Imaging channel
XML	eXtensible Markup Language

1.4. Document format and Repository

This document is compliant with the SIMBIO-SYS Report and Note Layout and Flow [RD.1] and will be archived on the SIMBIO-SYS ZENODO community (<https://zenodo.org/communities/?p=SIMBIO-SYS>), on the INAF Open Access repository and the SIMBIO-SYS team Archive.

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1.5. Document Organization

This document is organized in sections whose topics are listed as follows:

- Section 2 – ICO#06 objectives, with a brief description (see Section 8.2.2 of [RD.2] for details) of the functional tests we are going to execute
- Section 3 – ICO#06 implementation and validation, with:
 - a brief description of which Flight Operation Procedures (FOPs) and Payload Operation Requests (PORs) we are going to use to perform the required test
 - the results of the sequence validation using a Simulation Software developed within the team
 - an estimation of the required resources in terms of Data Volume, duration and expected number of frames for each sequence
- Section 4 – ICO#06 timeline, with the list of activities to be performed logically ordered to optimize instrument activations and test duration

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2. Test objective

The scope of the SIMBIO ICO#06 is the periodic (i.e., sixth) verification of the health status of the instrument at channel and system level. Few performance tests are also planned to monitor the evolution of some key instrument parameters.

Finally, an interference test with the S/C Thermal Adjustment System is performed.

2.1. Functional Test

During the ICO#06 the SIMBIO-SYS functionality shall be verified by means of dedicated Functional Test procedures on the following elements:

- HRIC, with the verification of:
 - PE, TEC and detector activation
 - memory/registers status
 - science acquisition capability
- STC, with the verification of:
 - PE, TEC and detector activation
 - memory/registers status
 - science acquisition capability

2.2. Performance Test

During the ICO#06 the SIMBIO-SYS performance shall be verified by means of minimal Performance test procedures on the following elements:

- HRIC, with the verification of the Dark Current (DC) behaviour for a reduced set of the nominal Integration Time (IT)
- VIHI, with the verification of its general performances and operability of all the major subsystems (TEC, Detector, Shutter, Lamp and LED).

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2.3. S/C heaters interference Test

To investigate for the possible origin of the detector reset fluctuation (i.e., Low Frequency Behaviour – LFB effect) present on both the HRIC and STC channels ([RD.3], [RD.4], [RD.5], [RD.6], [RD.7], [RD.8] and [RD.9]) an additional test is foreseen after switching off the S/C heaters that control the SIMBIO-SYS thermal environment. The test involves just the STC channel as it has a more direct contact with the S/C heaters ([RD.2]) and consists in repeating part of its functional test (i.e., science acquisitions one) once the S/C heaters are switched off to verify if the operativity such system affects STC Science acquisitions.

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3. Test implementation

3.1. Tools

Tests reported in the following sub-sessions shall be executed by means of proper FOPs, On-Board Control Procedures (OBCPs) and PORs listed in the following subsections and described in [RD.10], [RD.11] and Annexed files.

3.2. Available resources

As per ESA-ESOC official communication by Silvano Manganelli emails, the SIMBIO-SYS ICO#06 test will take place on 22/11/2021 at 00:00:00 UTC and the available time and Data-Volume resources will be:

- test duration: about 4 hours
- Data-Volume: about 250 Mbytes

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3.3. SIMBIO-SYS Functional Tests

3.3.1. HRIC Functional Test

3.3.1.1. Scope

The aim of this test is:

- to check the status and the functionality of the following electric components of the channel:
 - Proximity Electronic (PE),
 - Detector and
 - Thermo-Electric Cooler (TEC);
- to modify some configuration parameters;
- to perform a science acquisition.

3.3.1.2. Preparation

To execute this test SIMBIO-SYS shall be in the following status:

Unit	Status
ME	OFF (on the MAIN channel)
HRIC	OFF
STC	OFF
VIHI	OFF

Waiting for SIMBIO-SYS ME Application SoftWare (ASW) update which should also affect the parameters for the correct TEC activation, a dedicated TCs sequence has been prepared to upload the nominal TEC parameters. With reference to the **ESA-ESOC recommendation on the POR generation for the ICOs activities** (i.e., minimize the number of produced PORs to simplify their import and verification) this sequence has been included in the POR used for the test (see initialization step in following section).

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3.3.1.3. Description

A POR with **SPOT ID BPSS01092** and named **SIMBIOSYS_HRIC_ICO#06_functional_test** has been prepared which contains the following operations:

1. SIMBIO-SYS ME switch-on via OBCP
2. the dedicated TC sequence for the nominal TEC parameters upload
3. the HRIC functional test with a sequence of FOPs call that implements the checks listed in Section 3.3.1.1.

3.3.1.4. Validation

The POR **SIMBIOSYS_HRIC_ICO#06_functional_test** has been validated by means of a Simulation Software and produces the following results:

Sequence duration		00:28:15			
Sequence Data Volume					
-	ME	HRIC	STC	VIHI	Overall
Science	-	0.0236 [Gb]	0 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0.0236 [Gb]
HK	0.0189 [Mb]	0.5935 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0.6124 [Mb]
Total	0.0189 [Mb]	0.0242 [Gb]	0 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0.0242 [Gb]

To note that above resources computation have to be considered as upper limits since for their computation the Simulation Software needs to introduce some fake TCs (i.e., ME and channel switch-on) in order to reproduce the correct SIMBIO-SYS state for the analysis.

3.3.1.5. Expected Science data

In the following table it is reported the number of frames that are expected to be produced during the test:

HRIC		STC		VIHI	
TC	# frames	TC	# frames	TC	# frames
1	180				
-	180				

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3.3.2. STC Functional Test

3.3.2.1. Scope

The aim of this test is:

- to check the status and the functionality of the following electric components of the channel:
 - Proximity Electronic (PE),
 - Detector and
 - Thermo-Electric Cooler (TEC);
- to modify some configuration parameters;
- to perform a science acquisition.

3.3.2.2. Preparation

To execute this test SIMBIO-SYS shall be in the following status:

Unit	Status
ME	OFF (on the MAIN channel)
HRIC	OFF
STC	OFF
VIHI	OFF

See Section 3.3.1.2.

3.3.2.3. Description

A POR with **SPOT ID BPSS01095** and named **SIMBIOSYS_STC_ICO#06_init and func** has been prepared which contains the following operations:

1. the dedicated TC sequence for the TEC parameters upload
2. the STC functional test via FOP SS-TST-020 whose details can be found in [RD.10].
3. a science TC in continuous mode stopped by a STC Stop Science.

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3.3.2.4. Validation

The POR **SIMBIOSYS_STC_ICO#06_init and func** has been validated by means of a Simulation Software and produces the following results:

Sequence duration		00:31:55			
Sequence Data Volume					
-	ME	HRIC	STC	VIHI	Overall
Science	-	0 [Mb]	0.0626 [Gb]	0 [Mb]	0.0626 [Gb]
HK	0.0315 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0.5874 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0.6188 [Mb]
Total	0.0315 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0.0632 [Gb]	0 [Mb]	0.0633 [Gb]

To note that above resources computation have to be considered as upper limits since for their computation the Simulation Software needs to introduce some fake TCs (i.e., ME and channel switch-on) in order to reproduce the correct SIMBIO-SYS state for the analysis.

3.3.2.5. Expected Science data

In the following table it is reported the number of frames that are expected to be produced during the test:

HRIC		STC		VIHI	
TC	# frames	TC	# frames	TC	# frames
		1	30		
		2	33		
		3	60		
		4	60		
		5	270		
		Total	326		

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3.4. SIMBIO-SYS Performance Tests

3.4.1. HRIC Performance Test

3.4.1.1. Scope

The aim of this test is to perform several acquisitions in dark condition and variable integration times to monitor the DC evolution during the cruise phase.

3.4.1.2. Preparation

To execute this test SIMBIO-SYS shall be in the following status:

Unit	Status
ME	ON (on the MAIN channel)
HRIC	OFF
STC	OFF
VIHI	OFF

See Section 3.3.1.2.

3.4.1.3. Description

A POR with **SPOT ID BPSS01093** and named **SIMBIOSYS_HRIC_ICO#06_dc_test** has been prepared which contains repeated acquisition with different Integration Time (IT).

To note that, in order to minimize the Data-Volume request, above described POR is characterised by following points:

1. only the FPAN filter region of the detector will be acquired
2. the number of ITs which became 9 instead of 17
3. the number of repetition of each acquisition which passed from 10 to

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3.4.1.4. Validation

The POR **SIMBIOSYS_HRIC_ICO#06_dc_test** has been validated by means of a Simulation Software and produces the following results:

Sequence duration		00:05:20			
Sequence Data Volume					
-	ME	HRIC	STC	VIHI	Overall
Science	-	1.4864 [Gb]	0 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	1.4864 [Gb]
HK	0.0191 [Mb]	0.5040 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0.5231 [Mb]
Total	0.0191 [Mb]	1.4869 [Gb]	0 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	1.4869 [Gb]

To note that above resources computation have to be considered as upper limits since for their computation the Simulation Software needs to introduce some fake TCs (i.e., ME and channel switch-on) in order to reproduce the correct SIMBIO-SYS state for the analysis.

3.4.1.5. Expected Science data

In the following table it is reported the number of frames that are expected to be produced during the test:

TC	HRIC	STC		VIHI	
	# frames	TC	# frames	TC	# frames
1	9				
2	9				
3	9				
4	9				
5	9				
6	9				
7	9				
8	9				
9	9				
-	81				

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3.4.2. VIHI Performance Test

3.4.2.1. Scope

The test will be devoted to the accurate description and understanding of the Dark Current management. In nominal conditions, this sequence is executed by properly setting the "Dark Macro" parameter in the commanded Science TC but, since the new version of the ASW with the updated shutter current has not been uploaded yet, this sequence has been implemented step by step manually.

The sequence will include acquisition of the dark and of the LED signal, with different modalities of binning/compression and of dark acquisition and subtraction.

3.4.2.2. Preparation

To execute this test SIMBIO-SYS shall be in the following status:

Unit	Status
ME	OFF (on the MAIN channel)
HRIC	OFF
STC	OFF
VIHI	OFF

See Section 3.3.1.2.

3.4.2.3. Description

A POR with **SPOT ID BPSS01094** and named **SIMBIOSYS_VIHI_ICO#06_Performance** has been prepared which contains the following operations:

1. VIHI Power On and initialisation (TEC parameters upload)
2. Dark Frame Acquisition; Dark storage and no Dark Subtraction
3. Dark Frame Acquisition; no Dark storage and Dark Subtraction.
4. Dark Frame Acquisition; no Dark storage and Dark Subtraction;

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5. Dark Frame Acquisition; Dark storage; no Dark Subtraction
6. Power ON LAMP
7. Frame Acquisition, no dark acquisition, Dark subtraction and IBR=0
8. Frame Acquisition, no dark acquisition, no Dark subtraction and IBR=32
9. Frame Acquisition, no dark acquisition, Dark subtraction, Spatial and Spectra Binning, Binning sequence of frame x1 and IBR=0
10. Frame Acquisition, no dark acquisition, Dark subtraction, Spatial and Spectra Binning, Binning sequence of frame x1 and IBR=32
11. Frame Acquisition, no dark acquisition, Dark subtraction, Spatial and Spectra Binning, Binning sequence of frame x1 and IBR=63
12. Frame Acquisition, no dark acquisition, Dark subtraction, Spatial and Spectra Binning, Binning sequence of frame x2 and IBR=0
13. Frame Acquisition, no dark acquisition, Dark subtraction, Spatial and Spectra Binning, Binning sequence of frame x2 and IBR=32
14. Frame Acquisition, no dark acquisition, Dark subtraction, Spatial and Spectra Binning, Binning sequence of frame x2 and IBR=63
15. Power OFF LAMP
16. Power Off VIHI

3.4.2.4. Validation

The POR **SIMBIOSYS_VIHI_ICO#06_Performance** has been validated by means of a Simulation Software and produces the following results:

Sequence duration		00:21:30			
Sequence Data Volume					
-	ME	HRIC	STC	VIHI	Overall
Science	-	0 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0.0916 [Gb]	0.0916 [Gb]
HK	0.0245 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0.6856 [Mb]	0.7101 [Mb]
Total	0.0245 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0.0923 [Gb]	0.0923 [Gb]

To note that above resources computation have to be considered as upper limits since for their computation the Simulation Software needs to introduce some fake TCs (i.e., ME and channel switch-on) in order to reproduce the correct SIMBIO-SYS state for the analysis.

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3.4.2.5. Expected Science data

In the following table it is reported the number of frames that are expected to be produced during the test:

HRIC		STC		VIHI	
TC	# frames	TC	# frames	TC	# frames
				1	23
				2	23
				3	18
				4	10
				5	10
				6	10
				7	10
				8	10
				9	10
				10	10
				11	10
				12	10
				-	154

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3.5. S/C heaters interference Test

3.5.1. Scope

The aim of this test is to evaluate if the detector reset fluctuation on the STC channel is influenced by the SIMBIO-SYS Thermal Settings Adjustment procedure applied by the S/C through the activation of heaters 18 and 19 (see SS-FCP-015 in [RD.10]). This investigation is done by repeating the science acquisitions part of STC Functional test described in Section 3.3.2 after the S/C heaters power-off (nominally on during all the ICO activities).

3.5.2. Preparation

To execute this test SIMBIO-SYS shall be in the following status:

Unit	Status
ME	OFF (on the MAIN channel)
HRIC	OFF
STC	OFF
VIHI	OFF

See Section 3.3.1.2.

3.5.3. Description

A POR with **SPOT ID BPSS01096** and named **SIMBIOSYS_STC_ICO#06_heaters** has been prepared which contains just a science TC in continuous mode stopped by a STC Stop Science.

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3.5.4. Validation

The POR **SIMBIOSYS_STC_ICO#06_heaters** has been validated by means of a Simulation Software and produces the following results:

Sequence duration		00:16:10			
Sequence Data Volume					
-	ME	HRIC	STC	VIHI	Overall
Science	-	0 [Mb]	0.0010 [Gb]	0 [Mb]	0.0010 [Gb]
HK	0.0231 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0.6641 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0.6872 [Mb]
Total	0.0231 [Mb]	0 [Mb]	0.0016 [Gb]	0 [Mb]	0.0017 [Gb]

To note that above resources computation have to be considered as upper limits since for their computation the Simulation Software needs to introduce some fake TCs (i.e., ME and channel switch-on) in order to reproduce the correct SIMBIO-SYS state for the analysis.

3.5.5. Expected Science data

In the following table it is reported the number of frames that are expected to be produced during the test:

HRIC		STC		VIHI	
TC	# frames	TC	# frames	TC	# frames
		1	240		
-		-	240	-	

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4. Timeline

With reference to the tests described in the previous sections, the following timeline applies:

ID	Description	Estimated duration	Estimated Data Volume	XML file
1. SIMBIOSYS_HRIC_ICO#06_functional_test	SIMBIO-SYS ME switch-on via OBCP, HRIC nominal TEC parameters upload and HRIC functional test with memory read/write tests and 1 Science acquisition	00:28:15	0.0242 [Gb]	✕ BPSS01092_00201.BC
2. SIMBIOSYS_HRIC_ICO#06_dc_test	HRIC DC verification	00:05:20	1.4869 [Gb]	✕ BPSS01093_00201.BC
3. SIMBIOSYS_STC_ICO#06_init and func	STC nominal TEC parameters upload and STC functional test with memory read/write tests and several Science acquisitions	00:31:55	0.0633 [Gb]	✕ BPSS01095_00201.BC

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ID	Description	Estimated duration	Estimated Data Volume	XML file
4. SIMBIOSYS_VIHI_ICO#06_Performance	VIHI nominal TEC parameters upload and VIHI performance verification with nominal operative parameters	00:21:30	0.0923 [Gb]	✕ BPSS01094_00201.BC
5. SIMBIOSYS_STC_ICO#06_heaters	STC Science acquisitions with STC heaters off	00:16:10	0.0017 [Gb]	✕ BPSS01096_00201.BC